

International Association for Women's Mental Health

IAWMH Position statement

**Support of Pregnant Women's Access to Effective Mental Health
Treatment**

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IAWMH Statement in Support of Pregnant Women's Access to Effective Mental Health Treatment

The International Association for Women's Mental Health (IAWMH) is an international, multi-specialty, nonprofit organization with global membership from different disciplines. Over more than two decades, the IAWMH has been dedicated to improving the mental health of women worldwide by expanding the body of knowledge about women's mental health, promoting gender-sensitive autonomy-enhancing mental health services for women, and disseminating evidence-based information and best practices through its renowned international conferences, educational courses, newsletters, and published research through its official journal Archives of Women's Mental Health.

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This position statement is issued in response to the FDA Expert Panel on Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitors (SSRIs) and Pregnancy held on July 21, 2025, an event that the IAWMH Lead Experts and Executive Committee have followed with great concern. The panel presented alarming misinterpreted scientific data, which have been communicated to the public by some panelists in such a way that would only evoke feelings of fear, guilt, and uncertainty particularly among women suffering from depression who are currently pregnant or planning to conceive.

While the IAWMH respects scientific debate and encourages knowledge sharing, it emphasizes that accuracy and transparency in offering information on all treatment options (including risks of not being treated), comparative risks and benefits associated with each clinical decision must be comprehensive and grounded in the full body of evidence rather than shaped by unsubstantiated expert opinion or fragmented data.

The prescription of psychotropic medications in pregnancy and breastfeeding is a practice that should be approached with great scrutiny considering all aspects of the management plan and the range of different treatment options, rather than focusing on harms caused by individual medications. Although certain SSRIs have been associated with an increased risk to the developing fetus or adverse pregnancy outcomes, this should not be interpreted as a risk inherent to the entire class of SSRIs. It is paramount to emphasize that a detected association does not infer causation. To date, no cause-effect link was documented, and mental disorders as a confounder has often been mentioned as a limitation to the method of many studies ¹.

On average, antidepressants (SSRIs) have proven efficacy and considered as relatively safe in reducing depressive symptoms and helping pregnant patients achieve remission. The claim that the mode of action of SSRIs is not fully understood is no different from other drugs

used in medicine (some antidiabetics and analgesics, for example). Like all medications prescribed during pregnancy, SSRIs are not risk-free; no medication is risk-free to use during pregnancy, but this has not deterred physicians from using these medications to treat their patients. Likewise, this should not deter perinatal psychiatrists from prescribing SSRIs to severely depressed women who need the treatment.

Perinatal Mood and Anxiety Disorders (PMADs) affect one in five women, it causes distressing symptoms to the mother during the critical time of pregnancy, which, if left untreated, will have a negative impact on maternal mental and physical health, offspring well-being, family and social relationships and overall quality of life. Given the increasing rates of perinatal depression and the rise in maternal suicide rates, as well as the clear benefits of antidepressants (SSRIs) in improving functionality and quality of life, clinical guidelines on principles of practice place SSRIs among first-line treatments for severe depression². Equally important is the effectiveness of SSRIs in treating conditions like obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD) and posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) including child-birth related PTSD; some of these conditions can be quite serious for the mother if left untreated³.

The existing substantial evidence show that untreated mental illness has harmful repercussions on both the mother and offspring should not be overlooked in our discussions with our patients and fellow obstetricians, as there is accumulating confirmed evidence linking maternal distress to fetal brain programming as well as to pregnancy and birth adversities. Obscuring this information does not favor a well-informed decision-making discussion.

In this respect the IAWMH underscores that all reputable institutions offering professional training courses on perinatal psychopharmacology essentially includes extensive modules on principles of practice and focuses on individualized care, providing professionals specializing in perinatal mental health with the knowledge, skills and resources that enable them to provide balanced informed care, weigh benefits and risks, and support their patients and their families/carers in making informed decisions that best suit their lives^{3, 4}. This approach is consistent with longstanding clinical guidance, such as the *Guidelines for Perinatal Care by the American Academy of Pediatrics and the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists*, which advocate for collaborative, patient-centered care that balances maternal and fetal well-being⁵. Thus, the suggestion made by some panelists that perinatal psychiatrists routinely hide the risks of SSRIs is not supported by evidence. These are isolated incidents, not the norm, and framing them that way risks harming the doctor-patient relationship.

The IAWMH stands with the rights of pregnant women to have access to effective treatment to their mentally distressing symptoms. Leaving these women in a state of doubt, fear, and uncertainty, further adding to their suffering without offering other alternatives and without hope for symptom relief is causing harm to our patients and our practice.

Finally, keeping the mother well and the offspring safe requires intricate management including shared informed decision-making, carefully individualized prescription of medications as clinically indicated, balancing of benefits and risks, and provision of multidisciplinary informed care. Transparency in the communication of up-to-date substantiated information is crucial for ethical practice.

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